

A NOTE ON THE ACTION OF ALLYL MAGNESIUM BROMIDE ON LEAD CHLORIDE

K. V. VIJAYARAGHAVAN

Lead alkyls were originally prepared by the action of zinc alkyls on lead chloride (Buckton, *Annalen*, 1859, 109, 222) or by the interaction of sodium-lead alloy and alkyl iodides (Cahours, *Annalen*, 1862, 122, 67). Pfeiffer and Truskier (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1128) prepared lead tetraethyl by the action of ethyl magnesium bromide on lead chloride. Gruttner and Krause and their collaborators (*Ber.*, 1916, 49, 141) have prepared a large number of organic compounds of lead using this method. But no attempt seems to have been made to prepare lead tetra-allyl

To the Grignard reagent from 10 g. of allyl bromide, prepared as described by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 135) 10 g. (75% of theory) of finely powdered dry lead chloride were added little by little with stirring.

The solution became reddish orange on coming into contact with the lead chloride. This colour immediately disappeared and the whole solution assumed a yellowish tinge. Lead separated as a spongy mass. After all the lead chloride was added, the whole mixture was refluxed for half an hour, and the product decomposed with cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried over calcium chloride. Some yellow powder also separated along with the calcium chloride.

The ethereal solution was coloured yellow. As the ether was being distilled off, a yellowish amorphous solid began to separate. It was filtered off and the distillation continued. The same solid separated again. The ethereal solution contained lead in organo-metallic combination. The compound or compounds formed were unstable and were undergoing spontaneous decomposition. The yellowish solid separating was found to contain organic matter also. It was not merely lead oxide. Pfeiffer and Truskier (*loc. cit.*), Gruttner and Krause (*loc. cit.*) and Jones and Werner have observed a similar phenomenon in the preparation of lead tetraethyl by Pfeiffer's method. Most probably lead diallyl or lead triallyl or both are present in solution due to the incomplete self-oxidation and reduction of lead diallyl, for lead diphenyl and triphenyl are known as strongly coloured substances.

The work was not completed owing to the difficulty of obtaining distillable liquids or crystallisable solids from the ethereal solution.

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